

**LOW-FREQUENCY LIMIT-CYCLES IN URANS SIMULATIONS OF CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSORS:
ANALYSIS AND FLOW CHARACTERIZATION**

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an investigation of performance limit-cycles occurring in Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) simulations of transonic centrifugal compressor stages, at high impeller rotational speeds. The studied operating points are located beyond the peak pressure ratio and correspond to the lower mass flow rate points that converge but yet distant from the steady state simulation surge limits. The performance analysis is made on three different compressor stages. The performance limit-cycles resemble typical mild surge hysteresis, although they appear prematurely.

A further objective is to identify and to characterize the flow phenomena potentially responsible for such limit-cycles. A detailed investigation is carried out on one compressor stage. The observed limit-cycles occur at low-frequencies, and last for more than 10 rotor rotations. Pressure ratio fluctuations reach 15%-30% of the operating points of maximum pressure ratio. Mass flow rates show variations ranging from 50% to 90% of their mean values. The analysis relies on simulation runs over long physical time (more than 100 rotations).

The singularity of this work lies in the diverse post-processing methodologies developed and employed. Statistical and topological methods, Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) are applied to 3D fields.

Keywords: Unsteady Aerodynamics, Mild Surge, Centrifugal Compressor

NOMENCLATURE

a	Temporal POD coefficient
A	Eigenvector
C	POD spatial correlation matrix
f	Frequency
f_1	Fundamental frequency of the limit-cycle
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
h	Enthalpy
H	Matrix of a quantity obtained with h
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
\dot{m}_{std}	Standard mass flow rate
M	POD snapshots
N	Data points
POD	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
PS	Pressure Side
ϕ	Spatial POD mode
Π^{t-t}	Ratio of total-to-total pressure
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
Rot.	Rotation
SS	Suction Side
σ	Standard deviation
t	Time
T	Period
\mathbf{u}	Random vector used for POD
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
U, V, W	Velocity component matrices
\mathbf{V}	Fluid velocity vector
V_θ	Tangential component of \mathbf{V}
\hat{V}_{θ, f_1}	Fundamental frequency amplitude of V_θ
\hat{V}_{θ, ϕ^1}	Amplitude of first POD mode of V_θ
\mathbf{x}	Position of \mathbf{u}

1. INTRODUCTION

The URANS approach is an established method used in numerical simulation of fluid flows within the domain of turbomachinery. URANS is pertinent for predicting average compressor performances, such as efficiency and pressure ratio, and their temporal fluctuation. Moreover, these simulations aid in identifying and understanding aerodynamic losses as well as both aerodynamic and acoustic excitations. Specifically, it can get blade unsteady aerodynamic loadings, useful for further mechanical analysis [1]. Regarding these last points, a significant advantage of URANS over higher fidelity methods, such as Large Eddy Simulation (LES), is its turnaround time, meeting industrial demands for design and analysis [2].

In [3], URANS simulations were conducted on the Safran transonic centrifugal compressor stage Turbocel. It features axial inlet guide vanes, an unshrouded splitter-bladed impeller, a vaned and splitter-bladed radial diffuser and axial outlet guide vanes (Fig. 1c illustrates the Turbocel architecture without inlet guide vanes). The study combines experimental and numerical analysis of the stage performances and flow field, at partial rotational speed. The surge limit predicted by the URANS simulations is consistent with the experimental surge limit. Near this limit, URANS simulations converge toward limit-cycles, exhibiting performance fluctuations (pressure ratio and mass flow rate) of comparable magnitude with the experiments. These oscillations are associated with the low frequency fluctuation of a separation zone in the radial diffuser. However, although the order of magnitude of the limit-cycle frequency is consistent, its exact value is not accurately reproduced. Furthermore, at lower mass flow rates, the fluctuations from the URANS simulations disappear.

Moreover, Turbocel is simulated at high rotational speed in [4]. It appears that the last operating point converging toward a stable state is located near the peak pressure ratio. Beyond this limit, the fluctuations predicted by URANS do not seem to be physically consistent. This behavior contrasts sharply with other approaches that are reported in the paper (RANS, LES and experiments) which all provide stable operating points at significantly lower mass flow rates. In addition, LES results at reduced mass flow rates again reveal the development of a separation zone within the radial diffuser.

In the present paper, simulations of three distinct transonic centrifugal compressor stages operating at high rotational speed are investigated. The simulations exhibit high fluctuations of the performances at low frequencies for operating points where such behavior would not be expected. A detailed investigation of these fluctuations is carried out for all three stages, and an in-depth analysis of the flow field is conducted for one of them. The objective is to determine whether a coherent unsteady structure within the machine is responsible for the global performance oscillations, and, if so, to identify and characterize it. To this end, multiple dedicated post-processing methodologies are employed, including statistical approaches, FFT, and POD, all

applied to 3D fields extracted from simulations over long physical times.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Geometries

This paper focuses on a study involving three different transonic centrifugal compressor stages designed by Safran Helicopter Engines. Each compressor was designed with specific objectives of pressure ratio, mass flow rate, and rotational speed. Although all of them are intended for helicopter engine applications, operate at high speed, and feature transonic flow at nominal rotational speed. They are referred to as CC0, CC1, and CC2. As shown in Figure 1, compressors CC0 and CC1 have comparable geometries: both feature an unshrouded splitter-bladed impeller, a radial vaned diffuser, a 180-degree elbow and radial outlet guide vanes. The CC2 compressor stage features an unshrouded splitter-bladed impeller, a vaned and splitter-bladed radial diffuser, a 90-degree elbow and axial outlet guide vanes.

FIGURE 1: MERIDIONAL CUTS OF THE STUDIED CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSORS

2.2 Numerical setup

The numerical setup of all the simulations conducted in this paper follows a standard configuration commonly employed by industry in the turbomachinery sector (see [3]). The URANS solver used is elsA (from ONERA, see [5]). It uses a finite volume method. The turbulence model is the k- ϵ of Smith [6]. The simulated fluid domain is composed of a single blade passage for each row. The meshes are structured and have a size of about 3 million of nodes. The temporal discretization scheme is a second order implicit method with about 100 physical time steps per blade passing. The convergence of the sub-iterative process is set to reach a residual value of 10^{-1} , combined with a number of sub-iterations of about 10. The inlet boundary condition is defined with total pressure, total temperature and velocity angles. The outlet boundary condition is defined by the static pressure implemented as a quadratic throttle law of mass flow rate (see [7] for the formulation). The wall boundary condition is non-slip and adiabatic. The azimuthal boundary condition is a phase-lag periodicity, as the interface between rotor and stator [8]. The interface between the two stators is a mixing plane. URANS simulations are run, restarting from the RANS stable state, throttling until they converge to an established limit-cycle.

2.3 Robustness of the numerical setup

The URANS simulations for all three geometries predict operating points with high levels of performance fluctuations, apparently non-physical, occurring at mass flow rates well above the last stable RANS operating points (see Fig. 2). These URANS operating points exhibiting large fluctuations are defined as converging toward limit-cycles. These operating points are obtained while reducing the target mass flow rate. As the target mass flow rate is reduced, the convergence to a stable state requires an increasing number of rotations before suddenly settling into limit-cycles. The convergence toward limit-cycle spreads for a few tenths of target mass flow rate, after which the simulation diverges.

The numerical setup detailed in Part 2.2 has to be challenged to determine whether the emergence of the limit-cycle is sensitive. Table 1 summarizes the different tests conducted. The conclusion is that none of the tested parameters have a noticeable effect on the limit-cycle emergence.

Numerical parameter types	Parameters
Upstream boundary condition	Far-field ‘non-reflecting’ condition.
Downstream boundary condition	Choked nozzle [9] with supersonic static pressure condition.
Periodic boundary condition	360° calculation with sliding meshes.
Stator-stator interface condition	Interpolation with an azimuthal dilation.

Time integration scheme	2 nd order implicit method (residual at 10^{-2} , ≈ 20 sub-iterations); 1 st order explicit method (≈ 1000 physical time steps per blade passing).
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TABLE 1: NUMERICAL PARAMETERS TESTED FOR LIMIT-CYCLE SENSITIVENESS

2.4 Post-processing methodology

The singularity of this paper lies in the analysis of flow fields from URANS simulation running over more than 100 rotations and to investigate low-frequency phenomena. To accurately characterize these, simulations are run over about ten limit-cycle patterns after a periodic convergence is reached. Due to storage constraints and writing time, only the mass flow rate is extracted at each time step, while the complete flow field is extracted once per rotation, *i.e.* with the same rotor angular position. This process allows to reach a normalized frequency resolution of about $df/f_1 = 0.1$ with a FFT analysis. For these reasons, frequencies higher than half the rotational frequency are not available in the flow field post-processing.

For post-processing, several statistical methods are employed. The operating points in the performance map are obtained using a time average over one rotation. The limit-cycle is described by successive averages over one rotation without overlapping. The 3D fields are analyzed with time average and standard deviation methods over the last 140 rotations.

To complement the statistical description of the flow, two decomposition methods are employed: a frequency domain analysis using FFT, and an energetics-based approach using POD. These reduced-order models are computed using a limited number of harmonics (for FFT) and modes (for POD).

The FFT decomposition and reconstruction are applied on the mass flow rate signal at the radial diffuser inlet and to the tangential velocity at each node of the 3D fields. Due to the short signal length, the FFT method is highly sensitive to windowing effects. Therefore, a pre-processing step is required in order to enforce the signal to contain an integer number of performance limit-cycle periods.

POD is a method particularly used in fluid dynamics for extracting the most energetic structures from complex datasets [10]. The snapshot method [11] is employed for this purpose. To avoid the effects of mesh density variations, POD is applied on a uniform 3D-grid onto which the results are interpolated. The last 50 records are used as snapshots for this post-processing. The unsteady velocity vector field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is decomposed into an infinite set of spatial orthogonal functions $\phi^m(\mathbf{x})$ called POD modes. In practice, the velocity field is approximated with a finite number of M modes by:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{m=1}^{+\infty} a^m(t) \phi^m(\mathbf{x}) \approx \sum_{m=1}^M a^m(t) \phi^m(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

where $a^m(t)$ is the temporal coefficient that quantifies the amplitude variation of each POD mode.

The method decomposes the flow field into a set of spatial modes, ranked according to their associated fluctuating energy content. Each mode ϕ^m captures a specific spatial pattern, while the temporal coefficients a^m describe the evolution of these patterns over time. Here, the problem is solved in a spatially and temporally discretized form on a three-dimensional spatial domain. The type of discrete datasets considered is M uncorrelated velocity field realizations (named snapshots) in a plane consisting of N data points. The POD optimization problem is equivalent to solving the following eigenvalue problem:

$$CA = \lambda A \quad (2)$$

where C , the spatial correlation matrix, is adapted for compressible flow as proposed by [12]:

$$C = \left(UU^T + VV^T + WW^T + \frac{2}{\gamma - 1} HH^T \right) \quad (3)$$

where U, V and W are the matrices (of size $N \times M$) made of each velocity component for all velocity field realizations. H is the matrix of a quantity obtained with the enthalpy as $\sqrt{(\gamma - 1)h}$. The POD mode components $\phi_x^m(x), \phi_y^m(x), \phi_z^m(x)$ and $\phi_h^m(x)$ are obtained by projecting, respectively, U, V, W and H on the corresponding eigenvector A^m :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_x^m(x) &= U^T A^m; \phi_y^m(x) = V^T A^m; \phi_z^m(x) = W^T A^m; \\ \phi_h^m(x) &= H^T A^m \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The temporal coefficient $a^m(t)$ is determined by projecting vector components on the POD mode:

$$a^m(t) = U\phi_x^m + V\phi_y^m + W\phi_z^m + \frac{2}{\gamma - 1} H\phi_h^m \quad (5)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Performance fluctuations

The paper aims to analyze the performances of CC0, CC1 and CC2 compressor stages. In the three cases, high amplitude periodic fluctuations of the performances can be observed after the peak pressure ratio operating point. As shown in Fig. 2.1, the compressor performance evolution in time describes a large trajectory, named in this paper limit-cycle as defined in Part. 2.3. This phenomenon extends beyond the specific case of [3].

The RANS simulations, shown as colored full lines, are typical iso-speed lines for this type of compressor stage. For CC0 and CC1, the URANS operating points are close to the corresponding RANS iso-speed line, being slightly above for CC0 and slightly below for CC1. In contrast for CC2, the URANS operating points exhibit a noticeable offset from the RANS iso-speed lines, being positioned below. Therefore, it seems that this compressor stage is more sensitive to unsteady effects. The reported limit-cycles correspond to the operating points obtained when progressively reducing the target mass flow rate from the last URANS stable points.

FIGURE 2: COMPRESSOR PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS IN TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO (1) AND STANDARD MASS FLOW RATE FLUCTUATIONS OVER TWO PATTERNS OF LIMIT-CYCLE (2) FOR: a) CC0, b) CC1, c) CC2

The limit cycles observed across all compressors exhibit amplitudes and frequencies normalized by the rotational frequency of the same order of magnitude. Relative to the operating points of maximum total-to-total pressure ratio, the values for CC0, CC1, and CC2 vary by approximately 30%, 30%, and 15%, respectively. The standard mass flow rates vary by about 90%, 80%, and 50% of their mean value. The corresponding limit-cycle periods are about 13, 14, and 10 rotations.

The cycles resemble mild surge hysteresis (see Fig. 22 of [13]) and, most notably, the CC2 cycle. All three exhibit the characteristic behavior of returning close to the iso-speed line after a performance drop. It then regains performance, following more or less the iso-speed line, before dropping again, forming the limit-cycle. However, during the ‘recovery’ phases the cycles do not precisely follow the URANS stable state characteristics.

Figure 2.2 presents the mass flow rate at the radial diffuser inlet over the last two cycles for each compressor. Raw data, recorded at each time step, are presented versus reconstructed data based on the fundamental frequency and its first two harmonics. For each case, the signal origin is set at the lowest value of the reconstructed signal. Mass flow rate fluctuations in the reconstructed signal are associated with the performance limit-cycle. The high frequency mass flow rate fluctuations in the raw data are related to the impeller blade passing. The amplitudes of both the limit-cycle and blade passing fluctuations are of the same order of magnitude.

Starting from the lowest mass flow rate, CC0 and CC2 exhibit a mass flow rate increase over about one-third of the period, before decreasing monotonically. For CC1 the mass flow also rises during the first third of the period, then decreases slowly over about 4 rotations before decreasing as CC0 and CC2. The CC1 signal features stronger perturbations at low mass flow rates than the two others. This explains why the performance cycle looks chaotic compared to CC0. The CC2 cycle is the least affected, except for fluctuations associated with the blade passing frequency.

Figure 3 presents the mass flow rate fluctuations of CC1 at different interfaces throughout the stage over one cycle. All signals are normalized by the maximum value of the radial diffuser inlet signal reconstructed from FFT decomposition. The frequency of the limit-cycle remains constant throughout the whole stage, and its amplitude is unchanged from the domain inlet to the radial diffuser outlet. This is highlighted when plotting only the reconstructed signal using the methodology described previously (not shown here). Downstream of the radial diffuser outlet, the amplitude of the limit-cycle decreases, reaching about 75% reduction of mass flow rate fluctuations at the domain outlet. The amplitude associated with the blade passing frequency is maximum at the impeller outlet. It diminishes downstream of it until the domain outlet where it becomes negligible compared to the amplitude of the limit-cycle. Upstream of the impeller, the blade passing frequency is not detectable. Overall, the limit-cycle phenomenon appears to

dominate the compressor stage dynamics. Also, the signals measured on both sides of the interface between the radial diffuser outlet and the inlet of the radial outlet guide vanes overlap. It indicates that the mixing plane defining this interface is not the element responsible for reducing the amplitudes associated with the limit-cycle and blade passing frequencies.

FIGURE 3: STANDARD MASS FLOW RATE FLUCTUATIONS OVER ONE PATTERN OF LIMIT-CYCLE THROUGHOUT CC1 STAGE

3.2 Stage-wide flow analysis

This paper provides an in-depth analysis of the flow field, with a focus on the CC1 compressor stage. It exhibits the strongest performance disturbances close to surge.

Based on the limit-cycle frequency, the mean fluid velocity, and the mean static temperature, the acoustic wavelength of the limit-cycle frequency phenomenon is around 12 m (streamwise) and 8 m (counter streamwise). The characteristic length of the fluid domain of about half a meter is thus comparatively very short. This large disparity in scales indicates that the observed limit-cycle oscillation is not driven by an acoustic mode, as the acoustic waves cannot resonate within the computational domain. Moreover, the convection speed is much lower than the acoustic speed. Also, the limit-cycle phenomenon can exist because of the degrees of freedom induced by the downstream boundary condition. Consequently, a quasi-steady-state hypothesis could be considered for the mass flow rate, assuming that its variation is small during the travel time of an acoustic wave along the simulated domain. This implies that the mass flow rate is assumed to be the same at the inlet and outlet of the radial diffuser.

The analysis of the whole stage has the purpose of finding the rows exhibiting abnormal flow behavior and/or zones of high aerodynamic fluctuations. To prospect for zones of abnormal flow behavior, a time average of the velocity amplitude on 140 rotations (with one 3D field extraction per rotation) is first computed. Figure 4a presents the average of the velocity amplitude on a cut at 25% of the span height, which has been flattened in azimuthal direction and along the curvilinear

FIGURE 4: FIELDS OF VELOCITY AMPLITUDE ON CC1 COMPRESSOR STAGE AT 25% OF SPAN HEIGHT: a) TIME AVERAGE, b) STANDARD DEVIATION

abscissa. The discontinuities at each row interface arise because each row has a different number of blades, and thus a different azimuthal extent. The time-averaging method helps in identifying zones of low and high velocity within the stage. In this case, the velocity amplitude increases through the impeller. Then the velocity amplitude slowly decreases in the radial diffuser before remaining quasi constant in the radial outlet guide vanes. Using this first approach, the flow exhibits a typical behavior, with velocity increasing through the rotor and decreasing through the stators. No zones of extreme fluid velocity are observed throughout the stage. The velocity fields are similar on both sides of the radial diffuser blades. These observations hold at all span heights.

By increasing the statistical methods in order, the standard deviation of the 3D field has been computed. Figure 4b presents the standard deviation of the velocity amplitude at 25% of span height. The radial diffuser can be identified as exhibiting the highest values. A large zone of high standard deviation is present at the first third of the suction side of the blade. In this zone, the velocity standard deviation is approximately half the magnitude of the mean velocity. The flow is mostly fluctuating in this zone. Interestingly, the radial diffuser is also identified as the key component responsible for periodic fluctuations in [3] (*i.e.* in

another compressor at partial speed). For this reason, the following analyses focus on this specific row.

3.3 Radial diffuser flow analysis

The aim of this study is to localize fluctuating zones, to identify if they are linked with a particular flow structure, and, if so, to characterize them. To contribute to this analysis, fields of V_θ are analyzed, as this component exhibits the highest velocity levels and the strongest fluctuations.

Figure 5 presents a cut at 25% of span height projected on a plan with different post-processing methods. This height is chosen because all methods seem to highlight a three-dimensional zone of high amplitude located on the suction side of the radial diffuser at around the first third of the chord. The amplitude is the highest at this span height. The zone of high fluctuation seems to extend on half of the channel width.

The different post-processing methods reveal another zone of high fluctuations, but near the leading edge on the pressure side. This zone is relatively narrow compared to the previous one on the suction side. Its amplitude is significant compared to the field at pressure side and depends on the method used (whereas the high-amplitude zone remains consistent on the suction side, regardless of the method employed).

FIGURE 5: FIELDS OF TANGENTIAL VELOCITY FOR CC1 RADIAL DIFFUSER AT 25% OF SPAN HEIGHT: a) STANDARD DEVIATION, b) AMPLITUDE OF FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY COMPUTED BY FFT, c) FIRST POD MODE

3.3.1 Statistical analysis

To identify the phenomenon responsible for the limit-cycles, statistical analyses are initially conducted.

Figure 5a represents the standard deviation of tangential velocity, normalized by the highest value of the field. This particular component best describes the fluctuating behavior in this row. A large zone of high fluctuations is observed as described in Part 3.2. This zone has two extrema of high values, both located near the wall. The location of the highest value is around the center of the largest extremum; it is highlighted by a black cross.

This method reveals another zone of high fluctuations on the pressure side as described in Part 3.3. Its amplitude does not exceed 70% of the amplitude observed on the suction side fluctuating zone.

3.3.2 FFT analysis

A FFT post-processing on the tangential velocity is computed from the signal at each point of the 3D field. For a specific frequency, the amplitude field is thus known. Figure 5b shows the amplitude field of the limit-cycle fundamental frequency, defined as f_1 , at 25% of span height. The values are normalized by the maximum value. A zone of high amplitudes emerges at the suction side, in the same zone highlighted by the standard deviation method. The position of maximal limit-cycle frequency amplitude is well correlated with the maximum of standard deviation. With this method, two extrema of high values again appear. The left extremum spreads less than with the standard deviation method.

Figure 6 is the FFT spectrum of tangential velocity at the location of maximum amplitude of standard deviation (black cross on Fig. 5a). It gives information about the amplitude and frequency of the first 6 pikes, normalized by the amplitude and frequency of the fundamental. The fundamental frequency of this signal, f_1 , is matching the frequency of the limit-cycle observed in the mass flow rate signal.

The fundamental frequency f_1 and the frequency of rotation appear to be multiples. A complete limit-cycle pattern occurs over precisely 14 rotations of the impeller. It also appears that all pikes of the FFT are harmonics of the limit-cycle. The fluctuations in this zone are dominated by the limit-cycle frequency.

FIGURE 6: FFT SPECTRUM OF TANGENTIAL VELOCITY ON THE FLUCTUATING STRUCTURE AT THE CC1 RADIAL DIFFUSER SUCTION SIDE

A small zone of high fluctuations also appears near the leading edge on the pressure side. With this method, the tangential velocity amplitude does not exceed 50% of the fluctuation on the suction side zone.

3.3.3 POD analysis

A POD is computed from multiple 3D fields, using the methodology developed in Part 2.4, in order to find coherent structures in the radial diffuser.

The first POD mode (Φ^1), ranked by fluctuating energy, accounts for 55% of the total fluctuating energy. The second mode contributes only 15% of the total fluctuating energy. This indicates that the fluctuating phenomenon captured by the first POD mode predominantly drives the global fluctuations in the radial diffuser.

Figure 5c shows the amplitude field of the tangential component of velocity, from the first POD mode. A zone of high amplitude can be observed, which appears to have the same shape and location as the structure detected with the standard deviation and FFT methods. Again, a small zone of high fluctuations is localized on the pressure side, near the leading edge. The tangential velocity amplitude of this zone is about 60% of the amplitude of the suction side zone.

The POD analysis provides an additional insight: it underlines a zone of intense flow fluctuations both in amplitude and time. Furthermore, it reveals that this zone forms a coherent pattern, with fluctuations contributing to more than half of the total fluctuating energy.

Figure 7 shows the fluctuations of the temporal coefficient a^1 associated with the first mode. This coefficient exhibits a repetitive pattern with a period of precisely 14 rotations. Hence, as a^1 represents the temporal coefficient of the mode containing most of the fluctuating energy, the first mode oscillates at the same frequency as the structure identified from the FFT amplitude field of tangential velocity and the FFT of the mass flow signal. This analysis confirms that the structure oscillates at the limit-cycle frequency of the mass flow rate.

FIGURE 7: FLUCTUATIONS OF TEMPORAL COEFFICIENT a^1 OF FIRST POD MODE Φ^1

With this method, a single extremum of high-value appears in the high-amplitude zone on suction side, unlike the two other analyses that revealed two distinct extrema. This lower extremum is in fact captured by the third POD mode, which accounts for only 10% of the total fluctuating energy.

3.3.4 Analysis of instantaneous fields

Having detected a structure using various post-processing methods, located around the first third of the radial diffuser chord on the suction side, it is now interesting to examine how this structure behaves dynamically over time.

Figure 8 presents tangential velocity fields, normalized by the maximum value, at two different instants, again at 25% of span height. These instants correspond to the extrema of the mass flow rate at the radial diffuser inlet, shown on Fig. 2b. Be aware that the colorbar is not symmetric about zero. The two instants, labeled ‘Snapshot 1’ (Fig. 8a) and ‘Snapshot 2’ (Fig. 8b), are indicated on the mass flow rate curve with dotted red lines. Rotation 14 corresponds to the minimum mass flow in the pattern, while rotation 19 corresponds to the maximum.

Figure 8a shows a large zone of negative tangential velocity values, spreading over half of the radial diffuser. This zone of backflow is located on the suction side, near the blade wall, over the first third of the chord. It corresponds to the zones identified with the post-processing methods. When this zone of negative tangential velocity values is large, the mass flow rate is low. This backflow remains in this zone for a few rotations before being swept away when it is observed in the mass flow rate curve (see Fig. 2b) an increase.

FIGURE 8: INSTANTANEOUS FIELDS OF TANGENTIAL VELOCITY FOR CC1 RADIAL DIFFUSER AT 25% OF SPAN HEIGHT: a) ‘SNAPSHOT 1’ (ROTATION 14), b) ‘SNAPSHOT 2’ (ROTATION 19)

‘Snapshot 1’ is located near the portion of the limit-cycle highlighted by a red circle on Fig. 2.1b. It cannot be precisely located on the hysteresis because it is an instantaneous snapshot,

whereas the performances are time-averaged. When the negative tangential velocity zone is large and the mass flow rate is low, the total pressure ratio of the whole stage is low.

‘Snapshot 2’ is also characterized by a zone of negative tangential velocity values, but this time on the pressure side of the radial diffuser. It is located very close to the blade wall, again over approximately the first third of the chord, but starting right on the leading edge. The zone extends radially over about one-third of the channel. Unlike ‘Snapshot 1’, this zone is only identifiable in ‘Snapshot 2’ and no others. Because it is transient, even with high amplitude, it is not highlighted by the standard deviation. The POD identifies this zone as a coherent structure with the fourth mode, which represents about 5% of the total fluctuating energy.

‘Snapshot 2’ is located near the maximum of the mass flow rate curve (Fig. 2b). After this instant, the flow behaves as expected, without zones of negative velocity. On the pressure ratio characteristic, ‘Snapshot 2’ corresponds to the moment where the stage performance catches again the iso-speed line. The subsequent instants behave normally, reflecting that the stage performance remains close to the iso-speed before falling again when passing the last operating point that converges to a stable state.

A fluctuating local phenomenon has thus been detected in the flow, pulsating at the limit-cycle frequency in mass flow rate of the compressor stage. It accounts for more than half of the fluctuating energy in the radial diffuser. A topological analysis is therefore proposed to identify and to characterize this structure, considered as a primary contributor to the stage-wide fluctuations.

Figure 9 presents such an analysis of the structures on the suction side of the radial diffuser at the same instant as ‘Snapshot 1’. The view is oriented toward the leading edge, looking onto the suction side. Skin-friction lines are approximated by the velocity vectors next to the wall surfaces.

The occurrence of three-dimensional flow separation requires the convergence of skin-friction lines along a particular friction line named ‘separation line’. In closed separation, skin-friction patterns exhibit critical points (where friction is null) that delimit the separation line at the wall [14]. A critical point can be a node, a focus or a saddle point.

In Figure 9, F stands for focus and S for saddle point. Skin friction lines are shown in black, and the arrows highlight the critical points. The flow separation zone begins at the upstream critical point, which is the saddle point ‘S1’. It is located near the leading edge, on the corner with the hub. The blue arrow upstream of ‘S1’ represents the forward flow. Downstream of this saddle point, the flow exhibits backflow (green arrow), corresponding to the large zone of negative tangential velocity in Fig. 8a. At the saddle point, the flow is deviated toward the hub and blade surface (red arrows) and is ejected from the boundary layer.

Focus points are characterized by flow rotating toward or away from their center of rotation, with flow respectively entering or exiting the center. A succession of focus points and saddle points are identified downstream of ‘S1’. Focus points lie between two saddle points. However, attentive readers may notice that a saddle point appears to be missing from the figure downstream of the diffuser. In fact, it is not shown in the figure, but a focus point is located slightly further downstream, about two-thirds of the chord, closing the separation zone.

FIGURE 9: ‘SNAPSHOT 1’: SKIN FRICTION LINES ON CC1 RADIAL DIFFUSER SUCTION SIDE WITH CRITICAL POINTS HIGHLIGHTED

Since the separation occurs at the junction between the hub and the blade, this structure can be considered a corner separation. At this instant, this corner separation extends over half of the channel in the azimuthal direction, half of the span height, and half of the chord.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an analysis of performance fluctuations that emerged from near-surge URANS simulations for three different transonic centrifugal compressor stages, coming from distinct machines, at high rotational speed.

All three compressor stages exhibit high-amplitude performance fluctuations. The oscillations display a periodic pattern at low frequency, resembling mild surge, yet they occur at relatively high mass flow rates where such behavior would not be expected. The stages have comparable fluctuations with cycle periods ranging from 10 to 14 rotations, mass flow rate variations between 50% and 90% of its mean value, and pressure ratio fluctuations of 15% to 30% relative to the operating point of maximum pressure ratio.

A CC1 in-depth analysis of the flow is conducted on one of the stages in order to identify any structures that could be the source of the global fluctuations and, if found, to characterize them. This investigation relies on dedicated post-processing methods applied to 3D fields extracted from long physical time simulations (more than 100 rotations). The methodologies include statistical analysis, FFT, POD, and topological techniques. Each approach contributes to the overall analysis, providing complementary insights to the comprehension of the flow dynamics.

Statistical analysis reveals a fluctuating zone of high amplitudes on the suction side of the CC1 radial diffuser, between the hub and the blade. This fluctuating zone appears to oscillate at the frequency of the mass flow rate limit-cycle, according to frequency analysis. This suggests that this structure could be the source of the observed fluctuations. This zone seems to have a coherent structure, that represents more than 50% of the fluctuating energy, according to POD analysis. It is associated with the most fluctuating phenomenon in the machine. Topological analysis shows that the structure originates at the leading edge and extends along approximately two-thirds of the chord. It extends over half of the channel in both spanwise and azimuthal directions. The structure is interpreted as a fluctuating corner flow separation.

These fluctuations do not appear to be generated by the numerical setup, although its configuration allows them to develop. A physical structure pulsates within the machine. Its fluctuation makes the whole stage fluctuating. These fluctuations cannot be evacuated by the boundary conditions. They are convected to the static pressure outlet condition, piloted in mass flow rate and thus perturbed. The condition adapts, generating a pressure wave that propagates backward to the inlet condition. The inlet condition then adjusts, shifting the operating point. This information reaches the fluctuating

structure, which becomes further perturbed, and the phenomenon continues. This feedback loop ultimately leads to the mild-surge-like hysteresis observed in the performance. The available numerical parameters cannot handle these fluctuations, leading to simulations converging to non-physical operating points.

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